

THE COVID-19
PANDEMIC
AGENDA
REPORT

**The Bio-Engineered Virus,
Deadly Vaccines, Faked Pandemic And
Real Agenda They Never Wanted
You To Know About**

Disclaimer: This document is not intended to provide medical advice and the creators of this document are not medical doctors.

The claims you are about to hear have been triple verified via documents, scientists and several practicing Medical doctors nationwide and around the globe. The irony is that solid evidence has been hidden in plain sight. And none of this is "conspiracy theory". So regardless of what you or I want to believe, here are the facts.

The truth, facts and hard evidence about the virus, the vaccine and the pandemic are going to be so hard to believe that it sounds like a science fiction movie. Unfortunately it's not a movie and this is an example of how life is stranger than fiction. No it doesn't matter what you or I want to believe because facts are facts and evidence is evidence. Dr. Fauci, Bill Gates, the vaccine manufacturers and regulatory agencies manufactured a pandemic, have broken the law, deceived almost the whole world and intentionally launched an agenda that has killed people on every single continent.

They have used the willing media, high-profile personalities, church leaders and the medical industry in a deliberate attempt to indoctrinate you, infect you and target you based on their agenda including the Covid-19 nanotechnology tracking grid, ID2020, Agenda 21 and 2030 Agenda Sustainable Development. And just like the tracking app they put on your cell phone and didn't tell you, facts are facts whether you want to believe this or stick your head in the sands of denial. Either way, you are a part of their agenda. And you won't like what they have planned because it can affect your finances, health, safety, family and free will.

THEIR AGENDA IS MUCH BIGGER THAN A VIRUS, A VACCINE AND A PANDEMIC!

In 2002 Sars-Cov-1 emerged. And quietly, the WHO, the NIH, Bill Gates, the NIAID, the FDA and the CDC learned from the virus and how it could be used to meet their objectives.

Somewhere between 2003 and 2014 they embarked on a collaborative effort project to manufacture a lethal pathogen in a lab by using the coronavirus from a bat and bio-engineering it with what is called gain-of-function. That is where they add new dangers and capabilities to a pre-existing virus.

This bio-engineering was done at the University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill under the direction of Dr. Ralph Baric. Other participants included various departments at the University of North Carolina as well as Harvard University, the FDA, scientists from Switzerland, Wuhan China and other places. And when they finished their portion of bio-engineering this virus, the Baric team published a paper saying exactly what they did and how. We have a copy of that paper and you will see it in this presentation.

Some time between 2013 and 2014 the Obama Administration placed a ban on tampering with and bio-engineering of lethal pathogens. The National Institute of Health notified the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill and their funding was suspended. This is when the research and development was sent to Wuhan China and why Wuhan had the virus in the first place. And grant money mysteriously went to Wuhan from the United States. The Virology lab in Wuhan, China then completed the SCH014 virus that would come to be known as Sars-Cov-2 and what you have come to believe is Covid-19.

In 2017, several key things happened that are clues to this manufactured pandemic. John Bolton became the National Security Advisor under Donald Trump and Bolton quickly disbanded the pandemic team, ignored the 69-page Pandemic Response Guide created by the Obama Administration and fired the head of the pandemic team.

Meanwhile, Dr. Fauci while delivering a keynote address at an event also in 2017, announced that the Trump Administration "would encounter a surprise pandemic". How did he know this at least 2 years ahead of time? Because he knew that it was planned and the virus was created in a lab. Also that same here, not a coincidence either, the Trump Administration lifted the ban on lethal virus tampering and bio-engineering. And the plan went forward for the scheduled release of the virus set for 2019.

Donald Trump became aware of the real agenda and though he did not care about you, he did care about winning re-election. And when he discovered that he would be used as a scapegoat and lose the election over the pandemic, he started taking steps to expose it, just as Obama in 2014 provided clues at his speech in Bethesda, Maryland and taken steps to stop it. But Obama's efforts only delayed what Dr Fauci and others were determined to release.

Trump's steps included hijacking the federal task force briefings, pulling out of the WHO, exposing that the virus did come from a lab, replacing Dr Fauci, labeling those behind the pandemic, revealing hydroxychloroquine and saying that one day the virus would disappear. All true, especially if you understand the lifecycle of viruses. Even man-made viruses cannot last forever.

The virus, while created at UNC and completed in Wuhan, China, was preserved until the time for its scheduled release in 2019. The other reason it was released in Wuhan, China was because in October of 2019 the World Military Games were held in Wuhan. This was where 100 countries (including the United States) sent soldiers to compete in the military games and the ideal time to release a virus that would travel worldwide quickly.

The virus often called Covid-19 (but actually named Sars-Cov-2) was released in October of 2019. Not by coincidence, the exact same month and year that the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation and Johns Hopkins was running a pandemic exercise called "Event

201". An exercise that imagined what would happen if a dangerous and highly contagious virus came from China and spread throughout the world. This was not a coincidence and this was not a practice drill. It was the implementation of the real thing.

Also not by coincidence, a Chinese government spokesman accused the United States of releasing the virus. But this was not given much attention because most people didn't realize that America was in Wuhan, China in October of 2019.

By the time former President Trump initiated a travel ban, the soldiers had already returned from the world military games in Wuhan, China and several Chinese citizens had come to the United States, specifically to New York. The spread had begun in the United States and it was too late to stop it.

From that point there was a deliberate and concentrated effort in the United States to allow the spread of the virus under the guise of playing dumb by Dr. Fauci, the NIH, CDC, FDA and WHO.

In January of 2020, the CDC released tests that were contaminated with the virus itself. The CDC, FDA and various medical agencies knew that the virus was Airborne but they said nothing. And eventually it was discovered that former President Trump knew this as early as February of 2020. We knew in March of 2020.

All the safety precautions set up by the federal task force were set up to be ineffective and allow the virus to spread. This included 6th feet social distancing which was never enough distance, face coverings and generic masks that did not protect citizens from the virus, the sudden removal or disappearance of aerosol Lysol which could have been used to sanitize the air and kill the virus, the permission of ineffective kn95 masks to come into the United States by the millions, symptoms that were never accurate and virus tests that were heavily inaccurate.

The top regulatory agencies in America played dumb, even though this was not the first pandemic in our lifetime and only one of several outbreaks over the last few decades. But the American public fell for every bit of the deception, just as much of the world did. And because America's guards against the virus were dropped on purpose, the United States ended up having the highest infection rates and the highest death rates in the world.

But why allow the United States to become the largest testing ground? Because most Americans would not have a clue about what was coming. Because most Americans would choose to stick their heads in the sand and simply follow the medical industry blindly. Because most Americans valued their freedom and their rights more than their safety. And because most Americans are so easily influenced, indoctrinated and brainwashed.

Furthermore, America is the ideal lab because it has the CDC, the FDA, Johnson and Johnson, Pfizer, Moderna, Bill Gates, Elon Musk, all 5 major 5G cell phone networks, the Rockefellers and a host of other dark forces ready and willing to participate.

So in order to push dangerous vaccines, the Regulatory Agencies you have come to trust suppressed, discredited and disregarded effective Medical Treatments used by doctors all over the United States and all over the world.

But regardless of how much the media hyped the dangerous virus, this virus did not do nearly as much damage as they made it seem. They faked, manufactured and combined numbers from other medical conditions including the flu and pneumonia along with the pandemic virus and 500,000 people never died in America from Covid-19.

So while Sar-Cov-2 was in fact manufactured and bio-engineered as a Trojan virus, packed with several other lethal pathogens and

horseshoe bat coronavirus from Wuhan, it still was not as deadly as they made it seem. The entire purpose of the virus was to get unsuspecting guinea pigs to take the Vaccines, vaccines that are just as dangerous as the virus itself, if not worse. Vaccines with several purposes, all dark and all hidden in plain sight.

To extend the life of the virus in order to create enough time and fear amongst the people and get them practically begging for the vaccine, those who manufactured this pandemic released various strains of the virus which mutated and became different variants. But this can't last forever either. And while they try to scare you with these Boogeyman strains, the numbers of hospitalizations, infections and deaths are still dropping anyway. And they would have done so without a vaccine because viruses do not stay around forever. If you want proof, look at the 1918 Spanish flu and the 2009 pandemic, both of which just disappeared.

Because the virus is getting weaker, those who created this pandemic have stepped up vaccines before the virus dies out by itself, released more strains, suddenly discovered other variants and introduced funny math to manipulate the pandemic decline.

So what you have just read and are about to read, see or hear is the facts, proof and hard evidence of these claims. There are direct links in the pandemic agenda to 5G, all of the major cell phone networks, SpaceX owned by Elon Musk, the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation, GAVI, MIT, Moderna, Pfizer, AstraZeneca, Johnson & Johnson, Novavax, the NIH, FDA, CDC, NIAID and DrFauci, to name a few.

As the numbers continue to drop and America, its businesses and schools open back up, the virus that has been here all alone will spread again. But this is not the virus being a more lethal one nor more contagious. It is simply the social behavior of the people that gas and will spread the virus.

So what does the vaccine industry do? Create Moderna and Pfizer nanotechnology vaccines that reprogram your DNA and inject the worst parts of the virus into your body. **MRNA vaccines that are not safe and not effective**, unless you define “safe and effective” by the twisted medical definitions they use. A vaccine that kills, causes strokes and seizures, heart attacks and blood poisoning, convulsions and paralysis in many more people than they let you know about – unless you know where to look. And yes there is proof, also hidden in plain sight.

So what does Johnson and Johnson do in pretending to build a vaccine to attack the Covid-19 respiratory virus? Develop an vaccine with an “adenovirus” which causes respiratory problems and infections.

While what you have heard or read is an awful lot to take in and even believe, keep reading and listening because you are about to see the proof. And while those who created the virus, the Pandemic and the agenda want you to only believe what they say, the evidence actually exposes them and now thousands of doctors and scientists are speaking out. Its time to wake up because they are coming for you, whether you believe it or not!

Ignorance is not bliss. It is just ignorance that makes people easy targets. No more age innocence and it's time to wake up because

A Storm is Coming

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